

Soulla Swaray: "Rights denied ? The Paradox of Foreigner Rights in Cyprus"

GES 472: Diplomatic Thesis GAL

“Rights denied? The Paradox of Foreigner Rights in Cyprus

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Abstract

Cyprus, which is ideally situated at the meeting point of three continents—Africa, Asia, and Europe—has a complicated and rich history of migration that has changed throughout time. This paper explores the history of immigration to the island, emphasizing current events and the refugee crisis. It is backed up by a long list of references. It talks about migratory statistics, the historical context, and the difficulties Cyprus has in handling these dynamics. Thanks to a combination of economic prospects, geopolitical concerns, local regulations, and regional crises, Cyprus has evolved from an emigration country to a major destination for immigrants and asylum seekers. The current immigration and asylum systems require major reforms in order to adequately handle these issues and safeguard the rights of migrants and refugees. The essay underscores the importance of robust national policies and coordinated international efforts in managing migration and ensuring the protection of those seeking refuge.

Context of the Research

This section addresses the core issue that, despite Cyprus being an EU member state, foreigners encounter substantial challenges in integrating and accessing their human rights. The objectives of this thesis are to provide a comprehensive overview of the current legal framework and policies related to the integration of foreigners in Cyprus. By utilizing reports from various NGOs, the thesis will highlight the practical challenges and human rights considerations that arise. Furthermore, a brief outline of the thesis structure will be provided to guide the reader through the subsequent analysis.

Introduction

Cyprus, located at the intersection of Europe, Asia, and Africa, has a rich and complex history of migration. Its strategic position has historically made it an important trading hub, allowing for the movement of goods and people across continents. In recent years, Cyprus has become a crucial destination for refugees and migrants escaping conflict zones and seeking better economic opportunities. This essay explores the history of immigration in Cyprus, focusing on recent trends and the ongoing refugee crisis, supported by a wide range of references. It provides an overview of the historical context, migration data, and the challenges Cyprus faces in managing these issues. The patterns of migration in Cyprus are deeply influenced by its geographical and political conditions. The island's strategic importance has attracted various waves of migrants throughout history, each leaving a significant impact on its cultural and demographic makeup. Cyprus has shifted from being a country known for emigration to becoming a key destination for immigrants and asylum seekers. This change is driven by regional conflicts, economic opportunities, and the complex interactions between local laws and international geopolitical factors. In recent years, there has been a notable rise in asylum requests in Cyprus, highlighting the need for improvements in the country's immigration and asylum systems. These increases reflect the immediate needs of those fleeing conflict as well as broader geopolitical dynamics. While Cyprus has a comprehensive framework for managing migration, it still has several shortcomings, particularly in protecting the rights of individuals eligible for subsidiary protection. Addressing these gaps requires better national policies and stronger international cooperation.

1. Chapters

2. Cyprus' History of Immigration Including Recent Arrival of Refugees

With its advantageous location at the meeting point of Europe, Asia, and Africa, Cyprus has a complicated migratory history. Cyprus's geographical location and political conditions have impacted its migratory patterns, from its ancient function as a major trading hub to its current status as a hub for refugees escaping conflict zones. This essay examines the immigration history of Cyprus, emphasizing contemporary developments and the refugee crisis. It is backed up by an extensive list of references. The historical background, migratory data, and Cyprus's difficulties in handling these dynamics are all covered throughout the conversation.

2.1. Historical Context and Migration Trends

The migration history of Cyprus is closely linked to its geopolitical significance and historical conflicts. Positioned near Turkey, Syria, Lebanon, Israel, and Egypt, Cyprus has long been a nexus for various migratory waves.¹ The island's division in 1974, following the Turkish invasion, led to distinct migratory flows, with Greek Cypriots moving south and Turkish Cypriots moving north, exacerbating internal displacement.²

In the late 20th century, Cyprus transitioned from a country of emigration to one of immigrants. Economic growth in the southern part of the island during the 1990s and early 2000s created labor shortages, resulting in increased immigration. However, the 2012 economic crisis and subsequent austerity measures made the country less attractive for foreign workers, altering the immigration landscape once again.³

2.2. Recent Migration and Refugee Statistics

Recent migration and refugee statistics highlight significant trends and challenges faced by Cyprus. In 2017, Cyprus had the third-highest emigration rate and the second-highest immigration rate in Europe. By 2019, it had the highest number of asylum seekers relative to

¹ <https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/bueros/zypern/16001.pdf>

² <https://migrants-refugees.va/it/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2021/09/2020-CP-Cyprus-EN.pdf>

³ <https://www.macrotrends.net/global-metrics/countries/CYP/cyprus/refugee-statistics>

its population in Europe. The country recorded 191,900 international migrants, making up 16% of its total population, with a notable net migration of 25,000 immigrants between 2014 and 2019.

The EU-Turkey Agreements of 2016 on migration have transformed Cyprus into a preferred destination on the migratory route due to its proximity to the Syrian coast. Consequently, Cyprus hosts a disproportionately high number of refugees: 13,259 out of a total population of approximately 850,000, accounting for about 4% of the population. The political division of the island exacerbates migratory flows, with many asylum seekers entering from the northern territories controlled by Turkish troops and then moving south into the Republic of Cyprus.⁴

2.3. Refugee Statistics and Migration Data

Figure 1: Cyprus's net migration rate from 1950 to 2024.

The recent sharp rise in refugee numbers highlights the increased arrivals due to conflicts and crises in recent years. For example, the refugee population in Cyprus surged from 16,277 in 2021 to 29,280 in 2022, reflecting a significant increase.

This jump suggests that escalating conflicts or crises in the refugees' home countries are likely driving this influx.

Cyprus Refugee Statistics - Historical Data		
Year	Refugees Granted Asylum	Annual % Change
2022	29,280.00	79.89%
2021	16,277.00	16.29%
2020	13,997.00	13.70%
2019	12,311.00	11.90%
2018	11,002.00	12.38%
2017	9,790.00	15.48%
2016	8,478.00	20.05%
2015	7,062.00	37.93%
2014	5,120.00	31.99%

Source: Adapted from Macrotrend Net, 2024

⁴ <https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/bueros/zypern/16001.pdf>

Figure 2: Cyprus net migration rate from 1950 to 2024.

This bar chart indicates that the net migration rate in Cyprus shows a declining trend, indicating slowing immigration despite maintaining positive rates. For instance, the net migration rate decreased from 4.136 per 1,000 population in 2021 to 4.056 in 2024. This consistent decline suggests that economic conditions or changes in immigration policies might be influencing the overall immigration trend.

Source: Adapted from Macrotrend Net, 2024

2.4. Challenges and Responses

The increase in asylum applications presents several challenges for Cyprus. The country's asylum and immigration systems are under considerable strain, with significant delays in processing applications. To address these issues, Cyprus has collaborated with the European Asylum Support Office (EASO), receiving financial aid and expert assistance to improve processing efficiency.⁵

Many asylum seekers enter Cyprus via the northern territories controlled by Turkey, making the "Green Line" a complex and militarized border zone.⁶ This situation is further complicated by Cyprus's economic conditions and government policies aimed at reducing welfare benefits, which have made the country less attractive to migrants.

⁵ <https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/bueros/zypern/16001.pdf>

⁶ <https://migrants-refugees.va/it/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2021/09/2020-CP-Cyprus-EN.pdf>

The island's geographical isolation from the EU mainland also plays a crucial role. Despite being only 100 kilometers from Syria, Cyprus received one of the smallest numbers of Syrian refugees during the height of the Syrian crisis in 2015, with only 1,730 applications. The combined effects of economic challenges and restrictive government policies have contributed to this lower influx.⁷

2.5. Conclusion

Cyprus's strategic location, political divides, and economic upheavals have all contributed to its rich immigrant history. The island is now a popular destination for immigrants and asylum seekers, having changed from being a nation of emigrants. Significant increases in asylum requests have been observed in recent years, primarily due to economic opportunities and conflicts in the region, but also to the intricate interactions between domestic legislation and geopolitical concerns. To properly manage these issues and protect the rights of migrants and refugees, significant improvements are required to the current immigration and asylum systems. Cyprus will continue to play a major role in the larger framework of European migration as it navigates these complex difficulties. The island's history highlights how crucial it is to have strong national policies and coordinated international efforts to address the multifaceted nature of migration and to ensure the protection of those seeking refuge.

⁷ <https://www.macrotrends.net/global-metrics/countries/CYP/cyprus/refugee-statistics>

3. Human Rights in Cyprus: Asylum Seekers, Refugees, and Migrants

European Studies, understanding the human rights guaranteed by international treaties and conventions is essential, especially for refugees, migrants, and asylum seekers. Cyprus is specifically obligated to protect these vulnerable groups as a signatory to numerous international human rights instruments and as a member of the EU. An overview of the human rights that refugees, migrants, and asylum seekers in Cyprus are entitled to is given in this article, with particular attention paid to social welfare benefits, healthcare, education, vocational training, and assistance with integration.

3.1 Benefits of Social Welfare

Through a variety of social welfare programs, the Cypriot government guarantees the fundamental requirements of migrants, refugees, and asylum seekers. These advantages include access to necessary services, housing help, and financial assistance. The Guaranteed Minimum Income (GMI) is a benefit available to refugees and asylum seekers. Its purpose is to assist people who are in need. Welfare provisions of this kind are essential for assisting people in maintaining a respectable level of living and easing their assimilation into society.⁸

3.2. Medical Care

Cyprus ensures that refugees, migrants, and asylum seekers have access to essential medical treatments, as healthcare is a fundamental human right. These people get the same healthcare services as Cypriot citizens by international agreements and Cypriot law that give access to emergency care, medical care, immunizations, and public hospitals and healthcare facilities. Additionally, the government guarantees access to mental health care, which is crucial for people who have been traumatized or uprooted.⁹

3.3. Education

⁸ <https://help.unhcr.org/cyprus/refugees-rights-and-duties/refugee-rights/>

⁹ <https://help.unhcr.org/cyprus/applying-for-asylum/your-rights-and-duties-as-an-asylum-seeker/>

The protection of the rights of migrants, refugees, and asylum seekers is very crucial in the field of education. Cyprus complies with the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child by offering free primary and secondary education to all children, regardless of immigration status. The Ministry of Education has put in place certain initiatives to aid in the integration of international students, such as language instruction and cultural orientation, to enable them to adapt and achieve academic success.¹⁰

3.4. Vocational Training

To enhance the employability of migrants, refugees, and asylum seekers and allow them to make a financial contribution to Cypriot society, vocational training is crucial. The Human Resources Development Authority of the Republic of Cyprus co-finances job jobs to give people work experience. These programs assist GMI beneficiaries in making the shift from welfare to employment. Furthermore, the Cyprus Productivity Center provides vocational training programs through local municipalities and non-governmental organizations, mostly in Greek but also in English, to refugees and beneficiaries of subsidiary protection.¹¹

3.5. Support for Integration

To guarantee that migrants, refugees, and asylum seekers may engage fully in Cypriot society, integration help is essential. The government and NGOs provide a range of services to aid in integration. For example, the UNHCR Office in Cyprus created the "HelpRefugeesWork" online portal in partnership with the Cyprus Refugee Council to link refugees looking for work with companies and training providers. Along with language instruction and cultural orientation, the government offers several services to aid in the adjustment and integration of newcomers into the community.¹²

3.6. Reunification of Families

¹⁰ <https://help.unhcr.org/cyprus/refugees-rights-and-duties/refugee-rights/>

¹¹ <https://help.unhcr.org/cyprus/refugees-rights-and-duties/refugee-rights/>

¹² <https://help.unhcr.org/cyprus/refugees-rights-and-duties/refugee-rights/>

For those who are given refugee status, family reunification is a fundamental entitlement under the Cyprus Refugee Law. To avoid financial constraints, refugees may petition for family reunification with immediate family members who were left behind in their country of origin no later than three months after obtaining refugee status. There is a protection gap, nevertheless, as this entitlement does not apply to those who have subsidiary protection status.¹³

3.7. Nationality and Extended Stay

A recognized refugee or beneficiary of subsidiary protection's path to citizenship and long-term residency in Cyprus guarantees their eventual full integration into the community. It takes four things to become a naturalized citizen: financial stability, excellent character, linguistic competency, and continuous residency. After eight years of residency, refugees are eligible to petition for citizenship, whereas those with subsidiary protection must first ask to be granted a new status. After five years of lawful residence and fulfillment of certain requirements, one can apply for long-term residency, which confers rights comparable to those of Cypriot citizens.¹⁴

3.8. Conclusion

In compliance with international treaties and conventions, Cyprus has built a comprehensive framework to safeguard the human rights of migrants, refugees, and asylum seekers. The nation works to guarantee that these vulnerable groups can live honorable lives and make valuable contributions to society through social welfare benefits, healthcare, education, vocational training, and integration help. However, there are still gaps, particularly with regard to the rights of persons who are eligible for subsidiary protection. It will be required to resolve these disparities by ongoing efforts in order to fully realize the human rights of all foreigners in Cyprus.

¹³ <https://help.unhcr.org/cyprus/refugees-rights-and-duties/refugee-rights/>

¹⁴ <https://help.unhcr.org/cyprus/refugees-rights-and-duties/refugee-rights/>

4. Issues and Difficulties with Cyprus's Protection of Foreigners' Human Rights

Cyprus, despite its obligations under international and EU law, faces significant challenges in protecting the human rights of foreigners, including asylum seekers, refugees, and migrants. These are complex issues that include labor market hurdles, insufficient conditions upon arrival, procedural delays, restrictive migration rules, and restricted access to legal aid. Using reports and observations from many human rights groups and organizations, this essay conducts a thorough analysis of these issues.

4.1. High Rate of Migrant Inflows Relative to Population

Cyprus has seen a large inflow of migrants compared to the number of people who live there. Due to the island's remote location and stringent asylum laws, the number of refugees is still minimal compared to other Mediterranean nations like Greece and Italy. In August 2015, there were about 2,380 asylum applicants, 4,480 holders of subsidiary protection, and 1,160 refugees living in Cyprus. The number of asylum applications has increased significantly, especially from Syrians, but has remained relatively low due to the island's stringent policies and isolation from the rest of Europe.¹⁵

4.2. Restrictive Migration Policy

The government of Cyprus has implemented a limited migration policy that is commonly known as "proactive deterrence." Given that many asylum seekers are assumed to be economic migrants rather than true refugees, the goal of this technique is to make the conditions for receiving refugees unappealing. The efficacy of this approach is called into doubt due to the increasing volume of arrivals and the substantial obstacles that asylum seekers in Cyprus must overcome.¹⁶

¹⁵

file:///C:/Users/acer/Downloads/Report%20by%20Nils%20M%C5%BEnieks,%20Commissioner%20for%20Human%20Rights%20of%20the%20Council%20of%20Europe,%20Following%20His%20Visit%20to%20Cyprus%20from%207%20to%2011%20December%202015.pdf

¹⁶ <https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/bueros/zypern/16001.pdf>

4.3. Problems relating to Subsidiary Protection Status and Refugee Status

The majority of asylum seekers in Cyprus are granted subsidiary protection status by the government, which is less generous than full refugee status and does not allow for family reunions. The UNHCR has criticized this policy for failing to provide sufficient support for vulnerable people, such as those who have been victims of sexual abuse, torture, and trafficking. This policy has been especially harmful to Syrians.¹⁷ In 2014, subsidiary protection was awarded in 94.5% of favorable first-instance rulings, although only 5.5% of those verdicts resulted in refugee status. According to the UNHCR, a large number of Syrians escaping war fit the requirements for refugee status, however, they frequently only receive secondary protection.¹⁸

4.4. Administrative and Procedural Difficulties

Cyprus's asylum procedure is beset by protracted delays. According to reports, it can take the Asylum Service anywhere from two to three years on average to execute an application; in certain situations, it can take up to seven years. The protracted appeals process, in which the Refugee Reviewing Authority (RRA) may take three years or longer to make a decision, exacerbates these delays. The lack of time constraints for following application processes implies that applicants might not receive regularized status for a long time.¹⁹

¹⁷ <https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/bueros/zypern/16001.pdf>

¹⁸

file:///C:/Users/acer/Downloads/Report%20by%20Nils%20M%C5%BEieks,%20Commissioner%20for%20Human%20Rights%20of%20the%20Council%20of%20Europe,%20Following%20His%20Visit%20to%20Cyprus%20from%207%20to%202011%20December%202015.pdf

¹⁹

file:///C:/Users/acer/Downloads/Report%20by%20Nils%20M%C5%BEieks,%20Commissioner%20for%20Human%20Rights%20of%20the%20Council%20of%20Europe,%20Following%20His%20Visit%20to%20Cyprus%20from%207%20to%202011%20December%202015.pdf

4.5. Legal Aid Accessibility

In Cyprus, the availability of legal aid for asylum seekers is highly restricted. During the administrative phases of the asylum procedure, the state does not offer free legal aid. Asylum seekers are instead forced to depend on NGOs, which are mostly supported by the European Refugee Fund and UNHCR, for their meager legal assistance.²⁰ Since its inception, very few petitions for legal assistance have been approved in Cyprus due to the restricted nature of the system. Furthermore, the Advocates Law restricts attorneys from performing pro bono work, which further restricts access to essential legal assistance.

4.6. Conditions of Reception

In Cyprus, the conditions under which asylum seekers are welcomed are challenging. The main welcome site, Kofinou, is situated in a rural location with subpar housing and scant integration assistance. Pournara, another facility designed to handle emergency circumstances, continues to struggle with challenges of service effectiveness and coordination. Due to difficulties finding private housing and the combination of high rental costs and fewer benefits, a large number of asylum seekers are either homeless or living in subpar conditions.

4.7. Access to the Labor Market

Asylum seekers no longer have to wait as long to enter the workforce, but the available jobs are still very limited, low-skilled, and poorly compensated. There are no accommodations for individuals who are unable to converse in Greek, and this constraint makes it impossible for highly trained asylum seekers to obtain suitable jobs. Access to welfare payments for individuals unable to work owing to health concerns is further hampered by administrative barriers.

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file:///C:/Users/acer/Downloads/Report%20by%20Nils%20M%C5%BEnieks,%20Commissioner%20for%20Human%20Rights%20of%20the%20Council%20of%20Europe,%20Following%20His%20Visit%20to%20Cyprus%20from%207%20to%2011%20December%202015.pdf

4.8. Overview and Current Advancements

The government's approach has drawn criticism for failing to address core problems with its immigration and refugee policy and for frequently placing the blame for immigration shortcomings on the EU. The absence of strategies to help unaccompanied kids transition to adulthood and the lack of support for vulnerable groups have been noticed by the European Commission against Racism and Intolerance (ECRI) and other agencies. Rather than encouraging immigrants' integration into society, Cyprus's economic model, which depends on inexpensive migrant labor, maintains immigrants' marginalization and ghettoization.²¹

The government of Cyprus recently explored additional immigration policies, such as the creation of closed detention facilities for asylum seekers and advocated tighter restrictions over the Green Line. These proposals have faced strong opposition from human rights organizations due to concerns over their potential to undermine asylum procedures and human rights protections.²²

4.9. Applications for Syrian Asylum Are Suspended by Cyprus

Owing to a recent spike in immigration, President Nikos Christodoulides said that Syrian individuals' claims for asylum would no longer be accepted. The burden that processing asylum requests from Syrian refugees escaping the ongoing crisis has placed on Cyprus's infrastructure and resources is reflected in this decision. Uncertainty surrounds the length of the suspension, which affects those seeking asylum in Cyprus who are already there or who intend to go there. Cyprus's efforts to persuade the European Union to reclassify some areas of Syria as safe zones, allowing for the repatriation of refugees and relieving pressure on Cyprus's receiving infrastructure, are partially responsible for this decision.

The number of migrants increasing, and the suspension of asylum applications makes the situation of people living in receiving camps worse. People who are arriving from Syria are forced to remain in these camps, where their prospects are uncertain. Cyprus faces issues

²¹ <https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/bueros/zypern/16001.pdf>

²² <https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/bueros/zypern/16001.pdf>

related to migration that are influenced by regional circumstances, such as its closeness to conflict zones and the economic conditions in neighboring countries like Lebanon. The sudden spike in arrivals emphasizes how critical it is to address the root causes and improve processing and reception capabilities.²³

4.10. Conclusion

Cyprus has a difficult time defending the human rights of outsiders, especially migrants, refugees, and asylum seekers. The problems include everything from stringent immigration laws and protracted legal proceedings to subpar receiving facilities and restricted access to legal counsel. There are still large gaps in knowledge despite efforts to address some of these difficulties. To fulfill its international commitments, Cyprus must put in place more compassionate and effective regulations to guarantee that the rights of all foreigners are upheld.

²³ <https://www.dw.com/en/cyprus-suspends-syrian-asylum-applications/a-68814230>

5. Improving the Efficacy of Current Integration Initiatives for Foreigners in Cyprus

Cyprus, like many other countries, struggles with the difficult issue of integrating immigrants, refugees, and asylum seekers into its society. To complete this process, several issues about legal frameworks, career prospects, perceptions, and reception circumstances must be resolved. This paper aims to identify critical areas for improvement in the protection of foreigners' human rights in Cyprus by analyzing insights from a variety of sources, including local population perceptions, labor market integration data, analysis of integration initiatives, and legal capacity rights considerations.

5.1. Perceptions and Reception Conditions

A humanitarian catastrophe sparked by Russia's invasion of Ukraine on February 24, 2022, resulted in a large-scale migration of Ukrainians fleeing across Europe in search of safety. Cyprus has initiated temporary protection measures for these displaced people as part of the European Union's reaction. This project is in line with EU Council Implementing Decision (EU) 2022/382, which attempts to give people escaping the war both temporary and immediate protection. ²⁴

Figure 2: Records of Ukraine's Refugees

Source: UNHCR collation of statistics

²⁴ <https://www.moi.gov.cy/moi/asylum/asylumservice.nsf/All/71A7D6D56D2B4B49C22588010055092A>

Figure 3: Countries accepting Refugee Response Plan

Other European countries

Country	Data Date	Refugees from Ukraine recorded in country as of date ⁽¹⁾	Refugees from Ukraine who applied for Asylum, TP or similar national protection schemes to date ⁽²⁾
Albania	07/11/2023	7,495	35
Armenia	17/07/2023	605	605
Austria	13/05/2024	74,130	113,695
Azerbaijan	07/05/2024	4,160	155
Belgium	30/04/2024	79,545	84,130
Bosnia and Herzegovina	30/04/2024	225	225
Croatia	30/04/2024	25,450	26,305
Cyprus	30/04/2024	18,740	22,005
Denmark	28/04/2024	32,640	51,720
Finland	30/04/2024	62,140	69,075
France	31/03/2024	68,260	105,070
Georgia	30/01/2024	26,660	680
Germany	04/05/2024	1,161,170	1,082,910
Greece	31/03/2024	28,190	28,755
Iceland	31/03/2024	4,255	4,220
Ireland	16/04/2024	106,355	106,355
Italy	30/04/2024	170,580	193,080

With that, special arrangements for Ukrainian refugees have been outlined by the Republic of Cyprus Asylum Service. Temporary protection is available to anyone who was living in Ukraine before the war and had to flee. They have access to several rights because of their status, such as residency permits, housing and employment opportunities, health care, and child education. The EU framework that is behind this endeavor seeks to strike a balance between member states' attempts to manage the influx and offer sufficient assistance. Through the EU Migration Preparedness and Crisis Management Network, it guarantees a coordinated response with operational support from Frontex, the European Union Asylum Agency (EUAA), and Europol.²⁵

5.2. Challenges with Integration Initiatives

Figure 3 sheds light on the difficulties encountered by foreign nationals in Cyprus as well as the effectiveness of current integration programs. The report emphasizes how important it is to close the disparities in inclusiveness-related governance, policies, and practices on college campuses. The results show that whereas some colleges have inclusive policies in place, others don't have formal rules for students who are refugees. Furthermore, there is inequity in the way support services are provided; refugees are frequently left to handle the integration process on their own. The report emphasizes how crucial it is to improve support

²⁵ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv%3AOJ.L_.2022.071.01.0001.01.ENG&toc=OJ%3AL%3A2022%3A071%3AFULL

systems and interact with stakeholders to assist successful foreigner integration activities in Cyprus.²⁶

5.3. Integration of the Labor Market

One of the most important components of the whole process of integrating immigrants in Cyprus is labor market integration. Based on a recent data analysis, called "StatLink" highlights the prospects and limitations in this field. There are still differences in employment rates between immigrants and those who were born here, even with gains in immigrant education levels. In addition to increased unemployment rates and unstable work, immigrants also have difficulty finding possibilities for skill-level jobs. In addition, there are gender differences, with migrant women having a larger incidence of lower-skilled jobs and lower employment rates. Comprehensive integration programs that emphasize job possibilities, skill development, and language fluency are crucial to addressing these issues.²⁷

5.4. Rights to Legal Capacity

Respecting the rights of people with disabilities to legal capacity is essential to Cyprus's adherence to human rights standards. Concerns about the inadequate consideration of individuals with intellectual or psychosocial problems' consent in legal capacity-related actions are brought up in Reference D. The current legal framework does not fully recognize the CRPD, as problems like guardianship and substituted decision-making prevent complete recognition under the law. Ongoing initiatives, however, are aimed at aligning the legal capacity regime with the principles of the Convention on the Rights of the Person, with a focus on protected rights and supported decision-making.²⁸

5.5. Conclusion

At the end, having a comprehensive strategy that takes into account attitudes, reception circumstances, employment prospects, and legal capacity rights is needed to preserve foreigners' human rights in Cyprus. Cyprus may cultivate a more inclusive society that protects

²⁶ file:///C:/Users/acer/Downloads/From%20family%20to%20university.pdf

²⁷ <https://migrant-integration.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-08/Settling%20in%20report%20final%20EN.pdf>

²⁸ <https://rm.coe.int/16806db80a>

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the rights of all people, regardless of their nationality or origin, by strengthening integration activities, developing support mechanisms, encouraging labor market integration, and guaranteeing legal capacity rights. To effectively execute policies and practices that support the integration and well-being of foreigners in Cyprus, cooperation between government agencies, civil society organizations, and international players is vital.

6. Conclusion

The history of migration in Cyprus showcases its strategic significance at the crossroads of Europe, Asia, and Africa. From its ancient role as a trading hub to its current status as a refuge for migrants and refugees, Cyprus has continuously adapted to changes in human movement. Today, the island faces the dual challenges of managing increased immigration and protecting the rights of migrants and refugees amid complex political and economic conditions. Cyprus's strategic location, combined with its political divisions and economic fluctuations, has created a diverse immigrant population. The recent rise in asylum requests reflects both the economic opportunities available on the island and the conflicts in surrounding regions. However, the existing immigration and asylum systems need significant improvements to effectively manage these challenges and protect the rights of all foreigners. To address these complexities, Cyprus must implement more humane and efficient policies that align with its international commitments. This includes improving social welfare benefits, healthcare, education, vocational training, and integration support for migrants and refugees. It is crucial to address the disparities in rights for those under subsidiary protection. Continuous efforts are necessary to close these gaps and fully uphold the human rights of all individuals living in Cyprus. As Cyprus continues to play a vital role in the European migration framework, it is important to strengthen national policies and foster international collaboration. These measures are essential to addressing the multifaceted nature of migration and ensuring the protection of those seeking refuge. By enhancing its immigration and asylum systems, Cyprus can better fulfill its obligations under international treaties and conventions, creating a more inclusive and equitable society for all.

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